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1 Abbreviations

ASR: Area-Specific Resistance
BMEP: Brake Mean Effective Pressure
BoP: Balance of Plant
BTE: Brake Thermal Efficiency
BZCY: $\text{BaZr}_{1-x-y}\text{Ce}_x\text{Y}_y\text{O}_{3-\delta}$
CCS: Carbon Capture and Storage
CFD: Computational fluid dynamic
CMR: Compact Membrane Reactor
CO: Confidential
CR: Compression Ratio
D: Deliverable
DI: Direct Injection
DR: Degradation Rate
EGR: Exhaust Gas Recirculation
EIS: Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
EU: European Union
FC: Fuel Cell
FCS: Fuel Cell System
FESEM: Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy
HDDT: Heavy-Duty Diesel Truck
ICE: Internal Combustion Engine
I-V: intensity-voltage
JRC: Joint Research Centre
NG: Natural Gas
OCV: Open Current Voltage
PEFC: polymer electrolyte fuel cell
PFI: Port Fuel Injection
PP: Program Participants
PU: Public
RE: Restricted
RPMS: Rapid Prototype Engine Management System
SCE: Single Cylinder Research Engine
SEM: Scanning Electron Microscope
SUSD: Start-up and shutdown
T_EO: Engine Out Temperature
TEM: Transmission electron microscopy
TGA: Thermogravimetric Analysis
TPR: Temperature programmed reduction
WHTC: World Harmonized Transient Cycle
WP: Work Package
XRD: X-Ray Diffraction

2 Summary

This document defines in detail the list of requisites for the experimental activities, relative to Task 3.1 Analysis of the proposed technology fundamentals and system, so that the testing conditions represent the integrated system behaviour.

The purpose of this document is to understand how the operation principles such as the expected dynamics and fundamentals of each technology may synergize with each other. In this sense, a list of requisites for the experimental activities and sensitivity analyses have been elaborated so that the integrated system (CMR together with FC/ICE) complies with the required system characteristics with the minimum energy and fuel utilisation: multi-fuel capability, highly efficient energy utilisation, adequate dynamic response, CO₂-free emission through CCS and modularity/scalability.

3 Analysis of the technology fundamentals and systems

3.1 Compact Membrane Reactor Experimental Activities

In this section, a description of the experimental activities related to the Compact Membrane Reactor (CMR) will be provided. First, the primary components of the CMR, consisting of the electrochemical cell and catalysts, and the integration of the catalytic electrochemical reactor will be detailed. The fine-tuning of their functions and properties will be crucial for the technology validation, in that sense, each individual element and the integrated system will be researched. Subsequently, the developed integrated catalytic electrochemical reactors will be tested, increasing progressively the complexity of the assay and the extracted information: the joint catalytic hydrogen generation and electrochemical operation will be tested using different benchmark and optimized catalysts and cells.

3.1.1 CMR Primary Components

Primary components refer to catalysts and electrochemical cell materials (electrolyte and electrodes) of the compact membrane reactor (CMR) that will be developed in the project (Figure 1).

Figure 1. View of the CMR System. Illustration of the phenomena.

The progress in adapting materials formulation or textural properties in the reactor architecture will be used to manufacture the integrated compact electrochemical reactors, which are modular by nature. To start with, this process involves the manufacturing of the electrochemical cells, and subsequent integration of the catalyst, ensuring good gas exchange between the electrodes and the catalyst surface as well as efficient current collection (with low ohmic losses). Moreover, proper fixation and excellent fluid-dynamics in the catalytic chamber are required.

3.1.1.1 Electrolyte

The developed electrolytes will be based on $\text{BaZr}_{1-x-y}\text{Ce}_x\text{Y}_y\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (BZCY) materials. An essential requirement for the dense electrolyte is the achievement of a proper transport of protons (H^+) and a negligible electronic contribution. Different stoichiometries for BZCY-based oxides will be tailored to obtain the needed protonic transport and stability properties under the selected operating conditions. The main method to manufacture the electrolyte will be solid-state sintering. The electrolyte should be compatible with the rest of materials and stable in the operating conditions. Structural and morphological characterization will be performed by XRD and SEM. Electrochemical properties will be evaluated by means of DC-conductivity and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS).

3.1.1.2 Electrodes

Electrode materials for the anode and cathode will be fabricated, characterized and tested. The active transfer area of the electrodes has to be maximized in order to optimize the gas exchange and to ensure the proper charge-transfer reaction distribution along the whole electrode surface. To achieve this, electrodes must possess high electronic and protonic conductivity and, on the other hand, both electrodes must present thermochemical stability in the operating conditions. In addition, the porous electrode layers should show good attachment onto the electrolyte as well as chemically compatible. Structural and morphological characterization will be done in fresh and post-mortem states by XRD and SEM. Electrochemical characterization of the manufactured electrodes will be performed in symmetrical cells (same electrode coated in both sides of the electrolyte) by EIS.

3.1.1.3 Catalysts

The developed catalysts must ensure an effective, full conversion of the different fuels to hydrogen. Catalysts' performance and stability will be evaluated in a fixed bed reactor where different operating conditions such as temperature and pressure and fuel type will be studied for each catalyst. Structural and morphological characterization will be carried out in fresh and post-mortem states by conventional techniques such as XRD, TG, TPR and SEM. The hydrogen yield, stability and compatibility (by XRD and SEM) with the electrochemical cell will be thoroughly analysed and taken into account for the selection of the final set of optimized catalysts.

3.1.2 Integrated CMR Testing Protocols

The following protocols describe the testing facilities for compact membrane reactors (CMRs), steps to heat up/cool down, the H_2 pumping experiments and the reaction validation with different fuels that are planned to be performed to electrochemically characterized the performance of the fabricated devices.

3.1.2.1 Testing facilities in ITQ (CSIC)

Different reactors for catalytic and electrochemical testing are located in the Energy Conversion and Storage Group lab facilities in ITQ (CSIC) (<https://itqmembranes.itq.webs.upv.es>) (Figure 2).

Reactors for electrochemical characterization and testing of CMRs are automated, the main advantage of this system is its greater flexibility, designed to test single electrochemical cells and interconnectors. The main components include: oven with a max. temperature of 1100 °C, controlled amounts of the feed gases via flow controllers allowing a wide variety of gas mixtures and gas chromatograph to analyse the reacted gases. Electrochemical characterization of the samples will be carried out by means of IV-curves and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).

Figure 2. Reactor testing bench for CMR testing in ITQ (CSIC).

3.1.2.2 Protocols to heat up/cool down

Experimentally, CMR will be heated up/cooled down from room temperature to the desired temperature (550-750 °C) with the adequate heating ramp (1 – 10 °C/min). Both chambers could be monitored by gas chromatography to observe any possible gas leak. The leaks will be monitored by adding a known concentration of a tracer (He or N₂) to the gas feed and monitored over time.

3.1.2.3 H₂ pumping experiments

The electrochemical performance of the CMR will be evaluated by means of i-V curves, Open Circuit Voltage (OCV) and electrochemical impedance measurements (EIS) under H₂ pumping conditions, see Table 1.

Table 1. H₂ pumping conditions.

Parameter	Values
Fuel/feed flows	1-500 ml/min
Current density	0-2 A/cm ²
Temperature	550-850 °C
Pressure	1-30 bar

Firstly, H₂ pumping experiments without performing any reaction will be carried out to evaluate the Faradaic efficiency of the cell. In this case, H₂ will be fed in the reaction chamber and Ar will be used in the H₂ chamber. The H₂ production in the anode (H₂ chamber) will be analysed by gas chromatography to determine the Faradaic efficiency. Flow rates expressed as mL·min⁻¹ will be calculated at standard conditions. The Faradaic efficiency (η_F , Eq. 1) will be calculated from the theoretical H₂ production ($F(H_2)_{th}$, Eq. 2) determined by the Faraday's equation and the obtained H₂ flow quantified by gas chromatography $F(H_2)_{exp}$.

$$\eta_F = F(H_2)_{exp} / F(H_2)_{th} \quad (1)$$

where $F(H_2)_{th} = I/nF \quad (2)$

and n is the number of the transferred electrons and F the Faraday constant.

Transport properties are evaluated under a variety of conditions, allowing to compare the effect of temperature, current density and flow rates on the extraction.

3.1.2.4 Reaction validation

The joint catalytic hydrogen generation and electrochemical operation will be tested using different benchmark and optimized catalysts and cells. The validation will be based on the progressive evaluation of the reactor cells: (i) CMR working in reaction conditions with individual fuels and (ii) CMR working in reaction conditions with multi-fuel configuration.

These tests will enable the evaluation of the hydrogen extraction capacity under working conditions and the effect of different parameters such as temperature, pressure, current, flow rates and feedstock composition. Table 2 summarises the range of values to be considered for the different parameters mentioned above. During this experiment, hydrogen is produced from different fuels, and subsequently pumped to the H₂ chamber as consequence of the current application. The H₂ production and concentration of the formed products will be analysed by gas chromatography to determine the Faradaic efficiency and the reaction yield, respectively.

Table 2. Reaction conditions

Parameter	Values
Feed flows	1-500 ml/min
Current density	0-2 A/cm ²
Temperature	550-850 °C
Pressure	1-30 bar

The effect of the different parameters will be analysed for each individual feed mixture (NH₃, CH₄, and methanol or ethanol) and in multifuel configuration following the test protocol cycle in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Test protocol cycle implemented for CMR reactions.

1. Seal the cell following the protocols developed for the sealing. T After the sealing, the system is tested for leaks by using a gas tracer (He or N₂) and analysing with the gas chromatograph.
2. Membrane catalyst is activated at the required temperature. Heat up/cool down (see 3.3.2.2) to the target temperature. Once the temperature is stable, the system is again tested for leaks.
3. Change feed to operation conditions. Flow rates expressed as mL·min⁻¹ will be calculated at standard conditions.

4. Set the pressure to the selected value
5. Start and monitor the reaction. The Faradaic efficiency (η_F) will be calculated from the equation 1.t. The CMR will also be characterised by means of OCV, i-V curves and area-specific resistance (ASR). The electrochemical compression will be also evaluated.
6. Cool down (see 3.3.2.2).

3.1.2.5 Long term testing

Long term tests (> 500 h) will be performed under reaction conditions to evaluate the stability of the electrochemical system. Optimum operating conditions will be selected, and the target current density will be applied for more than 500 h while measuring electrochemical properties, H₂ transport (Faradaic efficiency) and reaction performance.

To characterise the electrochemical degradation, two main parameters will be monitored:

- 1) area-specific resistance (ASR) as a function of time (see Equation 3), where E_i is the voltage at a given current density i .¹

$$ASR = \frac{OCV - E_i}{i} = \frac{dE_i}{di} \quad (3)$$

- 2) degradation rate (DR) or average degradation rate (\overline{DR}) normally used to determine changes in efficiency over the lifetime of the cell, Equation 4 and 5.²

$$DR(t) = 100 \times \left(\frac{\frac{dASR(i,t)}{dt}}{V(i,t_0)} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\overline{DR}(t) = 100I \frac{ASR(i,t) - ASR(i,t_0)}{V(i,t_0) \times (t - t_0)} \quad (5)$$

3.1.2.6 Materials evolution

Degradation of the CMR performance can be related to the evolution of the materials composing the cells such as sintering, coarsening or poisoning, etc. In order to study the connection between the degradation rate and the evolution of the materials, different electrochemical and structural and morphological characterization techniques will be employed. EIS will be performed during the measurements whereas XRD, FESEM and TEM will be carried out after the measurements.

3.1.2.7 CMR electrochemical and fluid-dynamics simulations

Modelling calculations will be carried out in ASPEN PLUS V9.0 using the experimental data to replicate the behaviour of the CMR reactor. The model will be focused on the reaction system for hydrogen generation and electrochemical processes. This model will include the different behaviours considering the different fuels used. Hence, both inlet and outlet streams, the reaction system and the electrochemical behaviour will be different depending on the fuel used. The modelling will calculate the energies of the processes (heat and electric) and outlet streams (gas outlet and H₂) to be considered in the simulations of H₂ICE and FCS.

3.2 H₂ICE Experimental Activities

This document describes the requisites for the experimental activities and sensitivity analyses representative of the H₂SCE operation. Within the ALL-IN Zero Program it is planned to operate a Single-Cylinder-Engine (SCE) in order to research the optimum operation strategy of a Hydrogen powered engine in combination with a CMR (whereas the CMR is providing the required H₂ to the engine).

The Single Cylinder Engine has the advantage of higher degrees of freedom compared to a full engine. For instance, the amount of boost pressure, air mass flow, Intake and Exhaust valve Timings, etc., are freely adjustable and unlike on a full engine fully independent of the current engine load.

This makes a SCE the ideal research carrier for questions related to operating an engine together with a CMR.

For planning and adjusting the experimental activities an initial test-plan has been setup as well as a test cell-instrumentation plan. Furthermore, also the engine basic characteristics have been defined in order to give the other related parties (e.g., UPV for the test cell setup) a magnitude of the requirements for the test cell.

The following chapters describe these requirements as well as the planned testing activities and related boundary conditions. By this an efficient test-environment setup and a smooth testing campaign should be enabled.

3.2.1 Specification of Research Engine and Test Bed set-up

As described in the Summary chapter, it is planned to use a Single Cylinder Engine for the testing campaign. The SCE planned for the H₂SCE tests described herein is derived from a NG single-cylinder engine which was used for comparing High-pressure direct injection with conventional gas injection in a previous EU-funded research-project.³ Besides the great flexibility other main advantages of Single Cylinder Engines are less costs for prototype hardware and less assemble time for hardware changes on test bed.

Since single-cylinder engines (SCE) are externally charged they provide a degree of freedom in setting the operation points, like boost pressure and exhaust back pressure individually.

For the investigations of the operating concept this will bring the following particular benefits:

- Operation with rapid prototype engine control unit possible.
- One instead of six cylinders brings a cost reduction (cost intensive prototype parts).
- Drift or malfunction on prototype parts are relatively easy to detect.
- The operation of the engine is independent of turbocharger hardware (freedom in lambda, EGR rate...). That makes it possible to investigate combustion parameters and their sensitivity without the influence of thermodynamics.
- Parameters can be investigated independently. Lambda independent from gas exchange work, independent from MFB50%.

3.2.1.1 Test Cell Instrumentation

The single-cylinder research engine shown in Figure 4 will be provided by AVL, and will be built up in Graz, Austria. After building up all the hardware, the engine will be transferred and will be set up on test bed at UPV in Valencia, Spain.

Hardware set-up belonging to AVL responsibility:

- SCE base engine including:
 - Head + belt train + sleeve and adaption of valve train
 - Intake manifold runner with PFI injectors
 - Exhaust manifold adaptation part
 - Wiring harness + RPEMS control system (+sensors required for RPEMS)
- Provide Handbook with SCE description and operation requirements

Planned to be built up at the test cell facility of UPV

- Intake and exhaust vessel
- EGR system
- Pressure and temperature sensors (water, oil, low- and high-pressure transducer)

- Adaption of interfaces
 - Intake manifold runner
 - Exhaust manifold
 - Connection to water and oil circuit
- Water and oil conditioning system
- Fresh air supply including boost pressure control; back pressure control
- Fuel and lube oil

Figure 4: AVL single cylinder research engine, based on a 13l heavy duty gas engine

The AVL SCE is based on a 13l Natural Gas (NG) Heavy Duty Diesel Engine, which will be equipped for test bed operation. The requirements for the testbed operation are described below (more details):

- Bore x Stroke=135 x 150mm
- Compression Ratio= 13:1 (original, final CR to be defined)
- Swept volume=2.1l
- AVL RPEMS (rapid prototype engine management system) for closed loop lambda control
- DI H₂ injector (Liebherr) designed for 40bar injection pressure (max. injection pressure 60bar)
- PFI H₂ injector (Liebherr) designed for 15bar injection pressure
- Cylinder head with tumble charge motion
- Boost pressure control by an external boost pressure supply
- Back pressure control by one electrical actuated back pressure valve
- Hydrogen fuel pressure control by test bed control panel
- External coolant conditioning unit
- External oil conditioning unit
- Conditioning of the intake air
- Emission bench (e.g., AVL AMA) – measurement device for gaseous emissions
- AVL particle counter (or similar, required for parts of the measurement campaign)

- Hydrogen mass flow meter
- Air mass flow meter
- EGR mass flow (e.g., O₂ measurement in the intake manifold)
- High pressure transducer: AVL GH14DK (will be provided by AVL)
- Low pressure transducer: AVL GU21C (or similar) with external cooling
- AVL Indicom (or similar) for measuring in-cylinder pressure, injector current, voltage, valve lift, etc...
- Blow-by meter
- All equipment for safety related operation (H₂-sensors, automatic stop)
- Dyno
- All temperature and pressure sensors in the intake part, engine and exhaust part:
 - Intake air (before, after flap)
 - Intercooler (before, after)
 - Intake manifold
 - Exhaust manifold
 - Engine out
 - Coolant (engine, EGR)
 - Oil
 - Hydrogen
 - EGR

3.2.1.2 Engine Specification

The base engine is a single-cylinder engine, a derivate of a series production 13l gas engine used in trucks for on-road transportation. The 13l engine class (Diesel or Natural Gas) serves as the backbone of Long-Haul trucks in Europe and is widely used within Trucks all over the continent. As of today, all major Truck OEMs in Europe do have 13l engines in their portfolio. It is expected that these engines will continue to be used within trucks well into the next decade, in particular upgraded versions which will comply with the EUVII legislation which is expected to be introduced in 2027.

In the table below a comparison of the base-engine and calculations for hydrogen fuel for the 6 cylinder and single cylinder engine are given. The expected performance figures are estimations at this point and need to be confirmed / revised throughout the measurement campaign.

Table 3: Engine Specification for six-cylinder gas/six-cylinder hydrogen and single-cylinder hydrogen engine

	NG-6 Cyl.	H ₂ -6 Cyl.	H ₂ -SCE
Displacement [l]	12.9	12.9	2.147
Bore x Stroke [mm]	Ø135x150	Ø135x150	Ø135x150
Power [kW] @1900rpm	338	323.5	53.9
Spec. Power [kW/l]	26	25	25
BMEP [bar] @1100rpm	19.5	21.5	21.5
BTE [%] sweet spot	38	43	43
EGR System	w/o		with

Table 3 shows the initial specification of the H₂SCE, derived from the 6-cylinder Hydrogen engine which again is being derived from the 6-cylinder NG base engine. The estimated values for peak power, BTE, etc... are derived from previous investigations at AVL with another 6-cylinder H₂ engine in the same engine class.⁴ As the research program continues it is expected that the current estimations might slightly change into the one or other direction due to the derived investigation results. However, in general the depicted performance figures should act well as initial information, also for the definition of the other parts of the overall system (i.e., CMR & H₂SCE).

The current single cylinder engine has a cylinder head with DOHC (double overhead camshaft) and tumble charge motion (pent roof design). The DOHC enables a flexible valve timing, both on intake and exhaust side (cam phasing). The engine will be prepared for direct injection and for port fuel injection (PFI) in the intake port. The ignition system will be a production spark plug & ignition coil. From a 6-cylinder engine with similar size, some results of a performed WHTC (World Harmonized Transient Cycle), fuelled with hydrogen were also added to provide more information for CMR layout.

WHTC Schematic Figure

Figure 5: WHTC operating points

Table 4: hot WHTC results from 6-cylinder hydrogen engine

WHTC hot	Average	Peak
Power [kW]	56	267
MF_FUEL [kg/h]	4.7	30
MF_IA [kg/h]	408	1629
MF_EXH [kg/h]	418	1645
T_EO [°C]	347	431

These figures should give an indication of the peak- and average performance of the engine in a typical Truck cycle (here represented by the EUVI legal-cycle, a WHTC). The average performance of the engine should give an initial indication of the fuel-flow requirements for the CMR: The expected peak- and average exhaust gas temperature and mass-flow on the other hand should give an initial indication for the energy which could be provided from the engine towards the CMR. These key engine characteristics should give an initial input for the CMR sizing. This topic will be further detailed and elaborated within work package 3.3.

3.2.1.3 AVL RPEMS

The AVL RPEMS (rapid prototype engine management system) has full calibration access via ETK (special emulation memory) or CCP (CAN calibration protocol) depending on the used RPEMS generation. It provides a complete software structure to run a hydrogen engine:

- Pre-control of injection timing and quantity
- Pre-control of spark advance and dwell time

- Pressure control for hydrogen fuel supply
- Closed loop Lambda control
- EGR valve pre-control
- Boost pressure control (if necessary)
- Electronic throttle valve control (if necessary)
- Cam phasing
- Processing of all engine sensors signals (temperatures, pressures, mass flows...)
- CAN communication to test bed system in case specific signals are transferred from test bed instrumentation to engine controller

The AVL RPEMS is attached to the main engine Sensors and Actuators and is a key part of the engine itself, since it provides all the functions required to operate the engine. Whilst the RPEMS controls all engine I/Os, a testbed controller is still mandatory in order to control the engine speed (via the dyno controller) and to set the torque setpoint (via a virtual pedal or direct input into the RPEMS, e.g., boost pressure setpoint).

3.2.2 Test plan for the H₂SCE:

There will be two main investigations regarding comburent, one with fresh air and the other with oxygen.

3.2.2.1 H₂SCE air-combustion experimental characterization

- First experimental campaign using ambient air as a comburent.
- Objective is characterizing engine operation targeting zero NO_x emissions.
- The target of H₂SCE operation is best performance and efficiency in combination with CMR.
- H₂SCE will operate at stationary conditions.
- The following combustion parameter investigation items are planned:
 - Air-fuel ratio: swept in the range where combustion is stable.
 - EGR operation: to diminish gas temperature and NO_x emissions.
 - VVT operation: trade-off with EGR and lambda in order to maximize efficiency and minimize NO_x.
 - Compression ratio: trade-off between knocking resistance and engine efficiency.
 - Spark timing: explore H₂-consumption vs exhaust available enthalpy.
 - Port and direct injection: comparison for impact on fuel-efficiency vs. NO_x emissions behaviour.
 - Knocking: limiting performance factor.
 - H₂ purity: assess the effect of H₂ impurities on H₂SCE performance and emissions (considering that in case of CMR malfunction H₂ can be contaminated with other chemical species).

3.2.2.2 H₂SCE oxy-combustion experimental characterization

- Combustion within an O₂ and H₂O atmosphere (without N₂).
- Engine operation with different conditions of spark advance, hydrogen equivalence ratio, O₂ and H₂O composition.
- Target is optimizing global operation of the system, including the close coupling between the H₂SCE and the CMR.
- Experimental work will focus on a limited number of speed-load conditions, according to the expected H₂SCE operation in the powerplant:
 - Mixture composition evaluation: mixture dilution with extra O₂ and recirculated H₂O to maintain temperature limits
 - Spark advance evaluation: explore H₂-consumption vs exhaust available enthalpy
 - Low load operation - minimum flow

3.2.3 H₂ Sensitivity

A hydrogen engine is in general quite robust against H₂ and fresh-air impurities compared to a fuel-cell. Engines are operated all over the world under very harsh and rough conditions and often the fuel-quality (e.g., in terms of Sulphur content of Diesel-fuels) is relatively low. Whilst the engine H/W is in general quite robust against such impurities, the impact of H₂ impurities on engine performance and emissions is of very high interest. Therefore, it is planned to conduct a H₂ Sensitivity study as a part of the engine testing campaign. The Sensitivity study should demonstrate how much certain by-products to the H₂-fuel impact engine emissions (both gaseous and potentially also related to PM/PN). The following list shows which by-products to H₂ and which level of impurity is planned to test:

- Ammonia (NH₃): +- 3 Vol-%
- Methane (CH₄): +- 3 Vol-%
- Methanol (CH₄O): +- 3 Vol-%
- Ethanol (C₂H₆O): +- 3 Vol-%

All the upper chemical compounds are amongst others also used as fuels, contain Hydrogen, and can be used by the CMR to deliver H₂ to the SCE. Whilst under normal conditions the H₂ delivered from the CMR has very high purity, certain malfunctions of the CMR might potentially also lead to pollution of the H₂ dedicated to the engine. Therefore, the impact on emissions of an impurity of up to 3 Vol-% from each fuel will be tested on the engine testbed as well.

3.3 Fuel cell system experimental activities

Along this section, a preliminary description of the experimental activities to be carried out in WP7 of project ALL-IN Zero is provided. These activities mainly comprise steady-state and transient load profiles imposed on the FCS under varying operating conditions. Nevertheless, all these testing activities are required to integrate a polarization curve characterization protocol that is intended to be carried out at the beginning and at the end of each testing procedure to gather as much data as possible about the effect of the load profile and the operating conditions on the change in the polarization curve due to degradation.

In all the testing procedures described in this document, the voltage, current, FC stack electrical power, BoP power consumption will be measured to fully characterize the energy balance of the FCS. The temperature, pressure, and flow rates at the inlet of the anode and cathode will be measured as well in real-time to understand the flow consumption and the influence of the inlet flow conditions on the FCS performance. The energy available at the FCS exhaust will be quantified by means of measuring the cathode outlet temperature and applying the mass conservation equations.

In this section, the polarization curve protocol is described together with the set of experimental testing activities (steady-state and transient) intended to carry out during the project.

3.3.1 Polarization curve measurement protocol

When working with a fuel cell system, there are many properties (kinetic, ohmic, mass transport...) that can be measured in order to understand its behaviour. However, the easiest way to provide an overview of the performance of this kind of systems is to measure the polarization curve (i-V curve), which depends on the operating conditions. Therefore, a detailed measurement protocol based on in situ or electrochemical characterization techniques should be defined carefully.

General electrochemical characterization or in situ techniques mainly focus on varying current and voltage to understand the behaviour of the fuel cell. However, it is also possible to control other properties such as operating temperature, pressure, flow rate or humidity, as long as the purpose of these changes is to observe and understand the sensitivity of the stack voltage, thus efficiency, to them.

Since current and voltage have a direct relation, varying one of them implies changing the other. It could be possible to control either of these variables, but since the polarization curve represents voltage depending on the current, the measurement method chosen is the galvanostatic one (current control). This measuring procedure will be carried out as recommended by the JRC (Joint Research Centre) in PEFC power stack performance testing procedure, which means it will consist of 3 main phases: pre-conditioning, setting the operating conditions and obtaining the polarization curve.

3.3.2 Step 1. Pre-conditioning or warming-up procedure

Ensuring that the system is stable is critical before characterizing the fuel cell, and, if not, operate it until all conditions have been stabilized. For this purpose, the current density will be increased in steps of 100 mA/cm² until reaching 150 A (value between the operating limits).

When reaching the specified value, the stack will operate for, at least, 30 minutes or until the outputs are stable. This process is compulsory to avoid a non-steady behaviour of the fuel cell during future operation.

3.3.3 Step 2. Operating conditions

During the characterization of the polarization curve the current will be used as the control variable to change the load of the FCS. For each polarization curve, the operating conditions, defined by the thermodynamic properties of the inlet flows and the environment, will be fixed but could be changed to understand the sensitivity of the FC stack voltage to them. The polarization curve represents the overall behaviour of the FC; hence the current steps will go from the stack's minimum until its maximum acceptable value to fully characterize the FC stack performance: 62.5 A – 375 A.

The operating conditions will be chosen to represent a realistic situation while considering the existing recommendations and the data provided by the FC manufacturer. Preliminarily, they will be varied within the following ranges to characterize the FC polarization curve and its sensitivity to the operating conditions:

Table 5. Operating conditions for the polarization curve protocol

Variable	Value	Recommendation
T _{amb} (°C)	25	>50
ϕ _{fuel}	99,99999%	up to 100% H ₂
T _{fuel} (°C)	T _{amb}	>80
p _{fuel} (bar)	13	12,5 - 15
RH	55%	0-100%
λ _{H2}	1,5	1,1 - 1,5
λ _{air}	2,5	2 - 2,5

3.3.4 Step 3. Polarization curve measurement

The polarization curve will be obtained by changing the current from its minimum to its maximum value. During this process, it is very important to supply the correct amount of hydrogen and oxygen to the stack to avoid cathode/anode starvation, which would lead to damage to the system. Therefore, mass flow rates should be increased before increasing the current and decreased after decreasing the current. If during this process, any variable exceeds any of the recommended thresholds (Annex A Table 12), it will be stopped immediately.

The polarization curve will be recorded between an established set of points (k), after the warm-up procedure. After the measuring process has been carried out, the stack current will be taken to its starting point.

Figure 6. Polarization curve measurement procedure⁵

The variation of the current will be done in small steps to ensure the pseudo-steady-state behavior of the fuel cell system. The minimum number of points that will be taken is 15, as recommended. Nevertheless, this number could be increased if necessary to obtain the pseudo-steady-state behavior or to obtain higher resolution within a certain range of current values. The time between steps will be called dwell time (t_{dwell}) and, in order to allow the system to stabilize, it can be divided into 4 different time periods: equilibration, stabilization, acquisition and offset.

Figure 7. Polarization curve time steps⁵

The time step will depend on the stability shown by the system during the tests, so the stated value could be corrected when carrying out the experiments. However, the recommended t_{dwell} value should be over 10 minutes and its periods must follow the existing recommendations (Annex A Table 13). This procedure should be done at least three times to understand its accuracy. The results can be checked with the polarization curve given by the fuel cell's manufacturer

3.3.5 Testing plan overview

The WP7 of ALL-IN Zero project focuses on the use of a fuel cell system in a vehicle, so the testing procedures carried out will aim to solve future problems or questions of this application. Particularly, the operating conditions an FCS used in transport application is subjected to are load changing, SUSD (Start-up and shutdown), high power, and idling.

It must be considered that, since fuel cell systems technology is still under development, new investigation needs might appear during the following years and testing procedures for these matters may be added to the current agenda.

In order to understand the system in the most detailed way that is possible, the testing plan will be divided into steady-state and transient characterization.

3.3.6 Steady-state characterization

The steady-state characterization has 3 main parts: characterizing the polarization curve, database generation and fuel cell optimization. The first two are directly related, since recording the polarization curve data will allow the database generation together with the collected data from the start-up and the shutdown processes.

3.3.6.1 FC system characterization

The characterization of the polarization curve will be done as it is explained in the polarization curve measurement protocol. In addition, characterizing the start-up and shutdown processes (SUSD) will also be an activity of interest. The characterization of SUSD processes will allow checking how they affect the degradation process in the future. Understanding this degradation and being able to minimize it has high importance because it is known that a 33% of the degradation of vehicle FCS may come from the degradation mechanism triggered during the SUSD process. These procedures can be explained by splitting them into steps (based on elsewhere publication⁶):

Start-up

1. The FC is shut off, both anode and cathode are filled with air
2. H₂ and air are supplied to the anode and cathode respectively
3. The voltage increases and reached OCV
4. The cell is ready to operate, current is drawn

Shutdown

1. The current load is reduced to 0, voltage increases to OCV
2. H₂ and air are shut off, both anode and cathode exhausts are opened
3. Voltage slowly decreases as air enters the anode

Since the work with the fuel cell system will take different SUSDs for a long period of time, there is no need to conduct specific experiments to understand them. This characterization will be integrated in the rest of the tests by recording the start-up and shutdown data every time the cell is used. In this way, a database will be generated for different humidity and temperatures depending on the ambient conditions of every different testing scenario. Current, voltage, power and fuel consumption will be the recorded outputs that will allow the characterization of these processes.

3.3.6.2 FCS optimization through voltage losses and energy balance studies

The polarization curve is defined by the voltage losses that affect the fuel cell stack. Therefore, understanding these losses would lead to a better understanding of the fuel cell stack and to a way of improving its behaviour. Three kinds of losses will be considered depending on their importance along the polarization curve: activation, ohmic and concentration losses.

Figure 8. Schematic representation of the polarization curve⁷

However, the purpose of these testing procedures goes further than modelling the losses, which can be done by feeding the obtained results into their existing models. The main purpose is to find the operating conditions that allow the minimum voltage losses possible. For this purpose, the polarization curve protocol will be performed under different sets of operating conditions:

Table 6. Operating conditions for the polarization curve protocol

Variable	Value	Step
T_{fuel} (°C)	5 - 45	5
p_{fuel} (bar)	12,5 – 14,5	0,5
RH	50 - 100%	10%

Once the FC stack voltage losses are characterized, the energy consumption of the balance of plant (BoP) (auxiliary components in charge of conditioning the anode, cathode and coolant flows fed into the stack) will be evaluated and compared against the electric power produced by the stack at different currents. This will permit the characterization of the energy balance of the FCS by computing the FCS net power (FC stack electric power minus BoP consumption) and the identification of the main source of energy losses at different loads under varying operating conditions.

Finally, once the performance of the FCS has been evaluated, it will be re-evaluated under similar operating conditions but with moderate levels of anode poisoning to understand the FC stack performance degradation due to potential CMR failure.

3.3.7 Transient characterization

After the steady-state characterization, a transient analysis will be carried out to understand the difference in the performance when the fuel cell system is under dynamic conditions.

3.3.7.1 Characterization of the critical transient behaviour

Once the steady-state characterization has been done, a rough idea of a good operating point for the FCS will be known. Therefore, the operating conditions considered “optimal” by this point will be the ones taken to carry out the transient characterization tests. The transient characterization will be done taking into account the maximum ramps allowed by the fuel cell, which are 5 A/s to increase the current and 10 A/s to decrease the current.

The experimental procedure will be divided into 3 main parts:

- *Increasing and decreasing ramps:* used to check the behaviour under larger steps than the ones used in the polarization curve, which try to reproduce a steady behaviour. Based on elsewhere publication.⁸
- *High current steps testing:* use of large ramps to reproduce the behaviour of the FC under a significant change power demand. These tests will be carried out with different levels of stabilization time.
- *Random ramps set:* set of different ramps as a mix of the two previous scenarios. These tests will be carried out with different levels of stabilization time. Based on elsewhere publication.⁹

Firstly, the behaviour of the FCS under increasing ramps will be tested by using different current change rates allowed by the system.

Figure 9. Increasing-current ramp test

Then, the same procedure will be performed for decreasing ramps.

Figure 10. Decreasing-current ramp test time evolution.

The matrixes of the used data are presented below:

Table 7. Increasing and decreasing current test values.

Increasing currents				Decreasing currents			
t (s) 2 A/s	t (s) 4 A/s	t (s) 5 A/s	I (A)	t (s) 2 A/s	t (s) 5 A/s	t (s) 10 A/s	I (A)
0	0	0	62,5	0	0	0	375
300	300	300	62,5	300	300	300	375
318,75	309,38	307,5	100	312,5	305	302,5	350
618,75	609,38	607,5	100	612,5	605	602,5	350
643,75	621,88	617,5	150	637,5	615	607,5	300
943,75	921,88	917,5	150	937,5	915	907,5	300
968,75	934,38	927,5	200	962,5	925	912,5	250
1268,75	1234,38	1227,5	200	1262,5	1225	1212,5	250
1293,75	1246,88	1237,5	250	1287,5	1235	1217,5	200
1593,75	1546,88	1537,5	250	1587,5	1535	1517,5	200
1618,75	1559,38	1547,5	300	1612,5	1545	1522,5	150
1918,75	1859,38	1847,5	300	1912,5	1845	1822,5	150
1943,75	1871,88	1857,5	350	1937,5	1855	1827,5	100
2243,75	2171,88	2157,5	350	2237,5	2155	2127,5	100
2256,25	2178,13	2162,5	375	2256,25	2162,5	2131,25	62,5
2556,25	2478,13	2462,5	375	2556,25	2462,5	2431,25	62,5

After that, for the high current steps testing, the current will be increased in different size ramps and then it will be drawn back to its original current value. In this way, it will be possible to understand how different changes in current affect the fuel cell system. The stabilization time (time after the ramp to allow all the variables to stabilize) will be varied between 300 s and close to 0 s to evaluate the FCS response when not enough time is provided to reach steady-state conditions.

The chosen test values are shown in Table 8-9 and Figs. 11-12.

Table 8. High current steps (high stabilization time) test current-time values.

t (s) 2 A/s & -2 A/s	t (s) 4 A/s & -5 A/s	t (s) 5 A/s & -10 A/s	I (A)
0,00	0,00	0,00	62,50
300,00	300,00	300,00	62,50
318,75	309,38	307,50	100,00
618,75	609,38	607,50	100,00
637,50	616,88	611,25	62,50
937,50	916,88	911,25	62,50
981,25	938,75	928,75	150,00
1281,25	1238,75	1228,75	150,00
1325,00	1256,25	1237,50	62,50
1625,00	1556,25	1537,50	62,50
1693,75	1590,63	1565,00	200,00
1993,75	1890,63	1865,00	200,00
2062,50	1918,13	1878,75	62,50
2362,50	2218,13	2178,75	62,50
2456,25	2265,00	2216,25	250,00

2756,25	2565,00	2516,25	250,00
2850,00	2602,50	2535,00	62,50
3150,00	2902,50	2835,00	62,50
3268,75	2961,88	2882,50	300,00
3568,75	3261,88	3182,50	300,00
3687,50	3309,38	3206,25	62,50
3987,50	3609,38	3506,25	62,50
4131,25	3681,25	3563,75	350,00
4431,25	3981,25	3863,75	350,00
4575,00	4038,75	3892,50	62,50
4875,00	4338,75	4192,50	62,50
5031,25	4416,88	4255,00	375,00
5331,25	4716,88	4555,00	375,00

Figure 11. High current steps (high stabilization time) test current-time evolution.

Table 9. High current steps (low stabilization time) test current-time values.

t (s) 2 A/s & -2 A/s	t (s) 4 A/s & -5 A/s	t (s) 5 A/s & -10 A/s	I (A)
0	0	0	62,5
300	300	300	62,5
318,75	309,38	307,5	100
323,75	314,38	312,5	100
342,5	321,88	316,25	62,5
347,5	326,88	321,25	62,5
391,25	348,75	338,75	150
396,25	353,75	343,75	150
440	371,25	352,5	62,5
445	376,25	357,5	62,5
513,75	410,63	385	200
518,75	415,63	390	200

587,5	443,13	403,75	62,5
592,5	448,13	408,75	62,5
686,25	495	446,25	250
691,25	500	451,25	250
785	537,5	470	62,5
790	542,5	475	62,5
908,75	601,88	522,5	300
913,75	606,88	527,5	300
1032,5	654,38	551,25	62,5
1037,5	659,38	556,25	62,5
1181,25	731,25	613,75	350
1186,25	736,25	618,75	350
1330	793,75	647,5	62,5
1335	798,75	652,5	62,5
1491,25	876,88	715	375
1791,25	1176,88	1015	375

Figure 12. High current steps (low stabilization time) test current-time evolution.

Finally, the last transient test will consist of applying a random set of ramps to the fuel cell. Again, a matrix of the chosen values is represented in Table 10-11 and in Fig. 13-14. Again, the stabilization time will be varied between 300 s and close to 0 s to evaluate the FCS response when not enough time is provided to reach stable conditions.

Table 10. Random current ramp (high stabilization time) test values.

t (s) 2 A/s & -2 A/s	t (s) 4 A/s & -5 A/s	t (s) 5 A/s & -10 A/s	I (A)
0,00	0,00	0,00	62,5
300,00	300,00	300,00	62,5
418,75	359,38	347,50	300
718,75	659,38	647,50	300

758,75	675,38	655,50	220
1058,75	975,38	955,50	220
1116,25	998,38	967,00	105
1416,25	1298,38	1267,00	105
1533,75	1357,13	1314,00	340
1833,75	1657,13	1614,00	340
1923,75	1693,13	1632,00	160
2223,75	1993,13	1932,00	160
2331,25	2046,88	1975,00	375
2631,25	2346,88	2275,00	375
2678,75	2365,88	2284,50	280
2978,75	2665,88	2584,50	280
3073,75	2703,88	2603,50	90
3373,75	3003,88	2903,50	90
3393,75	3013,88	2911,50	130
3693,75	3313,88	3211,50	130
3753,75	3343,88	3235,50	250
4053,75	3643,88	3535,50	250
4123,75	3671,88	3549,50	110
4423,75	3971,88	3849,50	110
4548,75	4034,38	3899,50	360
4848,75	4334,38	4199,50	360
4997,50	4393,88	4229,25	62,5
5297,50	4693,88	4529,25	62,5

Figure 13. Random current ramp (high stabilization time) test current-time evolution.

Table 11. Random current ramp (low stabilization time) test values.

t (s) 2 A/s & -2 A/s	t (s) 4 A/s & -5 A/s	t (s) 5 A/s & -10 A/s	I (A)
0	0	0	62,5

300	300	300	62,5
418,75	359,38	347,5	300
423,75	364,38	352,5	300
463,75	380,38	360,5	220
468,75	385,38	365,5	220
526,25	408,38	377	105
531,25	413,38	382	105
648,75	472,13	429	340
653,75	477,13	434	340
743,75	513,13	452	160
748,75	518,13	457	160
856,25	571,88	500	375
861,25	576,88	505	375
908,75	595,88	514,5	280
913,75	600,88	519,5	280
1008,75	638,88	538,5	90
1013,75	643,88	543,5	90
1033,75	653,88	551,5	130
1038,75	658,88	556,5	130
1098,75	688,88	580,5	250
1103,75	693,88	585,5	250
1173,75	721,88	599,5	110
1178,75	726,88	604,5	110
1303,75	789,38	654,5	360
1308,75	794,38	659,5	360
1457,5	853,88	689,25	62,5
1757,5	1153,88	989,25	62,5

Figure 14. Random current ramp (low stabilization time) test current-time evolution.

The presented set of studies will be carried out for the conditions that would have been found to be optimal during the characterization study (temperature, pressure and humidity). However, it could also be a matter of interest to test 2 other set of conditions to check the difference in the transient behavior. During these studies, voltage and power will be important output parameters to study. Nevertheless, it should not be forgotten that other variables such as hydrogen and oxygen consumption and the power of the compressor could also be interesting outputs to measure.

3.3.7.2 Testing under standardized and realistic driving cycle conditions

Once the transient behaviour has been tested, for the future use of the FCS in heavy-duty applications it will be useful to test some real driving cycles. The proposed driving cycles will be HDDT (standardized) and TENT routes-based cycles (real driving).

HDDT (Heavy-Duty Diesel Truck) are standardized common velocity profiles for heavy-duty applications which can be converted into current profiles by using an appropriate model. In this case, the cruise and transient segment cycles will be the chosen cases to test.

Figure 15. Speed profiles for the chosen HDDT cycles¹⁰

In contrast, realistic driving load profiles based on TENT routes represent the most common paths that are used by heavy-duty vehicles around Europe.

Figure 16. Example of TENTec routes around Europe¹¹

After the vehicle model is fully defined, the load profiles will be obtained by simulating the heavy-duty virtual vehicle under these routes. GPS-based models such as MAPBOX, capable of predicting the velocity behaviour on a certain route, will be used to define the FCS current profile in the experimental facility.

3.3.7.3 Hysteresis of the polarization curve

During transient operation, the polarization curve defining the stack performance may change depending on the operating conditions and the rate of change of the current. As such, a dedicated analysis will be carried out based on the already defined tests.

The high current steps testing and random steps protocols defined in Tables 7-8 and Figs. 11-12 will be used to understand under different operating conditions, current levels and dynamics the hysteresis level of the polarization curve. Furthermore, the standardized and realistic driving test will be used to understand if the hysteresis affecting the FC stack performance changes when it is operated as part of a powertrain for a heavy-duty vehicle, compared to the previous testing. The standard deviation of the voltage along the polarization curve will be computed for each transient testing, thus providing meaningful information to feed up energy management strategy algorithms required for the control of the power generation system.

3.3.7.4 Degradation of the polarization curve

The polarization curve establishes the relation between current and voltage in a fuel cell system and it is well-known that it is the best way to show its overall behaviour. However, its behaviour may change after a certain usage period due to the degradation of the components in the membrane electrode assembly (gas diffusion layers, catalyst layers and membrane).

The purpose of the degradation tests will be to understand how the polarization curve changes after testing, mainly transient, and try to reduce this phenomenon by acting on easily controlled parameters such as temperature, pressure and relative humidity, such as the previously explained experiments.

The polarization curve will be measured after what should be considered a realistic driving cycle for a fuel cell truck, following the protocol defined in section 3.1. It will be done each time for the different proposed operating conditions (Table 6) to check their influence on real performance and, also, the way in which they may modify the polarization curve.

Annex A

Table 12. Recommended alarm values and emergency thresholds. [1].

Criterion	Symbol	Alarm	Emergency
1	V_{min}	$0.3 \cdot n \text{ V}$	$0.2 \cdot n \text{ V}$
2	$V_{i, min} (1 \leq i \leq n)$	0.3 V	0.2 V
3	ΔV_i	<i>according to stack manufacturer recommendation</i>	
4	I_{max}	<i>according to stack manufacturer recommendation</i>	
5	T_{stack}	+ 3.5°C versus T_{stack} set point	+ 5°C versus T_{stack} set point
6	$T_{cool, out}^*$	+ 3.5°C versus T_{cool} set point	+ 5°C versus T_{cool} set point
7	$T_{fuel/ox, out}$	+ 3.5°C versus $T_{fuel/ox}$ set point	+ 10°C versus $T_{fuel/ox}$ set point
9	ΔT_{cool}^*	> 2K above stack manufacturer's recommendation	> 5K above stack manufacturer's recommendation
8	$p_{fluid, in}$	<i>according to stack manufacturer's recommendation</i>	
10	$\Delta p_{fluid, max}$		
11	$\Delta p_{fuel-to ox, max}$		

Table 13. Recommended parameters related to test steps. [1].

Symbol	Value	Unit
t_k	$(k - 1) \cdot t_{dwell}$	[min]
t_{dwell}	$t_{eq} + t_{stab} + t_{acq} + t_{offs}$	[min]
t_{eq}	<i>according to load ramping & adjustment of reactant flow rates</i>	[min]
t_{stab}	$\geq 2 t_{acq}$	[min]
t_{offs}	<i>according to envisaged delay in data acquisition by the test bench</i>	[s]
t_{acq}	> 1	[min]
t_{smp}	1	[s]
m	$\frac{t_{acq}}{t_{smp}} + 1$	-
$t_{k,l} (0 \leq l \leq m-1)$	$t_k + t_{k,eq} + t_{k,stab} + l \cdot t_{smp}$	[min]

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